

Maxwell-Boltzmann Maximum Entropy as a Guarantor of Stability and Order?

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Maximum entropy is traditionally considered a signature of maximum disorder within a system with the word “disorder” having apparently a negative connotation. The idea of maximum disorder seems to follow from the following information theory argument (1). Consider a set of probabilities $\{ p(i) \}$. For a very large number of events N , event i should appear $Np(i)$. Thus the overall product probability is: $P = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(i) \text{ [to the power } Np(i)\text{]}$. This may be written as $\exp(\text{Sum over } i \text{ } N p(i) \ln(p(i)))$. The probability may be written as $1/\text{number of arrangements}$ thus maximizing $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i)\ln(p(i))$ maximizes the number of arrangements i.e. maximizes disorder.

In (2) we showed that one may obtain Shannon's entropy by seeking a vector dot product $S = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) G(p(i))$ such that $dS = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } G(p(i)) dp(i)$. $G(p(i))$ then becomes $\ln(p(i))$. The benefit of this is that $G(p(i))$ remains constant for small $dp(i)$ fluctuations. In fact, for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case it may be compared to an average conserved quantity which in general follows the form: $A_{\text{ave}} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } A(i) p(i)$. $dA_{\text{ave}} = 0$ (conservation) = $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } A(i) dp(i)$. This has the same form as S so in some cases, such as the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) one may link the two directly i.e. $A(i) = \ln(p(i)) + C$. Given that A_{ave} cannot change under changes $dp(i)$, it is stable. If $S = -\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i))$ also does not change with changing $dp(i)$ (holding T temperature constant and box size as well with $A(i)$ being energy e_i) then it too must be stable. In the MB case $A(i) = e_i$ i.e. energy of state i . Thus it is stability which we argue is the key idea to entropy and Shannon's entropy form which under $dp(i)$ mimics a conserved average quantity which is stable i.e. remains unchanged. One does not need to think of disorder or large N in such an approach. Entropy (which mathematically does follow from a maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint of a conserved quantity) is equivalent up to a constant to the conserved quantity at least in the MB case. The fact that there is maximum disorder shows we argue that this allows for stability i.e. allows for a kind of restoring mechanism if one changes probabilities i.e. $dp(i)$. This restoring force seems to be linked to two body scattering which follows from $\ln(p_{\text{relative}}(i)) = -e_i/T$.

Entropy and Disorder

Entropy is often associated with maximum disorder (which has a negative connotation), but we argue that an ideal gas as an entity is ordered. One parameter T (temperature) describes a constant average energy in space and density and pressure are constant as well. Small fluctuations do not break the “equilibrium” (order) and one may further create ordered sound waves in such a gas. Thus maximum disorder creates a kind of restoring force to ensure stability is maintained. Before considering this idea we examine why maximum entropy is associated with disorder (1).

Consider a set of probabilities $\{ p(i) \}$ where i is a particular outcome (e.g. tossing a coin or die etc). If one has a large number N of outcomes, each i should appear $Np(i)$ times. The product probability is:

$$\text{Probability} = 1/\text{arrangements} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(i)^{Np(i)} = \exp(-N \sum \text{over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i))) \quad ((1))$$

To maximize the number of arrangements i.e. disorder one may maximize $-\sum \text{over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i))$ which is called Shannon's entropy. Thus entropy is considered as a quantity which measures disorder. Often one has a constraint which is linked to a conserved quantity e.g. $\sum \text{over } i \text{ } p(i) = 1$ or $\sum \text{over } i \text{ } e_i p(i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. One may maximize Shannon's entropy with respect to the constraint to find $p(i)$ values which yield the maximum disorder. Thus disorder seems to be a physical idea associated with entropy.

In the next section we argue that stability is the main idea associated with entropy and that one does not really need to maximize to find $p(i)$ even though mathematically there is nothing wrong with maximizing subject to a constraint.

Entropy as Function Which Changes Like a Conserved Constraint

A main idea we wish to suggest is that entropy is a function which under a change $p(i) \rightarrow p(i) + dp(i)$ behaves like a conserved average quantity. For example, consider conserved average energy:

$$E_{\text{ave}} = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } e_i p(i) \quad ((2))$$

If T temperature is kept constant and box size as well then E_{ave} is conserved i.e. a constant. Thus:

$$dE_{\text{ave}} = 0 = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } e_i dp(i) \quad ((3))$$

Fluctuations leading to $dp(i)$ should die out because overall E_{ave} is a stable or conserved quantity. The question then becomes: Is there a function of $p(i)$ namely a dot product $S = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } p(i) G(p(i))$ such that $dS = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } G(p(i)) dp(i)$ i.e. it changes like a conserved quantity? In (2) we argue that $G(p(i)) = -\ln(p(i))$ is such a quantity. In fact, for the case of E_{ave} , one has:

$$\ln(p(i)_{\text{relative}}) = -e_i/T \text{ so } p(i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ where } T \text{ is parameter (temperature)} \quad ((4)) \text{ and}$$

$$E_{\text{ave}} - TS = -T \ln C(T) \quad ((5))$$

In other words E_{ave} and $TS = -T \sum \text{over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i))$ differ by a constant i.e. $-T \ln(C(T))$ if T is held constant (and L box size too). Thus if E_{ave} is stable to fluctuations $dp(i)$, then S must also be stable. Thus entropy is a function which mimics a conserved quantity under changes $dp(i)$ at least in the MB case we consider here. There is no need for any idea of large N or disorder to arrive at this result although there is nothing wrong with considering these. They are also linked to the idea of entropy, but we argue that the key idea is stability which marks equilibrium. If a small change undoes an equilibrium state then it is unstable.

Two Body Scattering

To see how the entropy may lead to stability consider ((4)) for which $\ln(p(i)_{\text{relative}}) = -e_i/T$. If one considers $p(i)$ and $p(j)$ one has:

$$\ln(p(i)) + \ln(p(j)) = \ln(p(i)p(j)) = -e_i/T - e_j/T \quad ((6))$$

Thus $p(i)p(j) = p(k)p(l)$ as long as $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. This may be considered as stochastic two body scattering which is equivalent to the entropy scenario. The probability for i and j to scatter elastically is given by:

$$p(i)p(j) \quad ((7))$$

If one has too much of a state i , then scattering helps to recreate equilibrium it seems. Furthermore there is a loss of information in the sense that any $p(i)p(j)$ such that $e_i + e_j = E$ yields the same product probability in equilibrium. This appears to be an extra idea associated with equilibrium for the MB case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, entropy is usually described as a measure of disorder and it is argued that it should be maximized subject to constraints on conserved quantities. Thus maximum disorder seems to be the main idea of entropy. We argue that stability is a more important idea, although the idea of disorder is also present. The main goal of equilibrium is to have a state which is stable to small fluctuations so it may last for a long period of time. Equilibrium e.g. an ideal gas seems to be ordered in the sense that it has constant energy density proportional to T , constant density and pressure. Furthermore one may establish ordered sound waves within it. It does not seem like a disordered state.

We argue that a conserved quantity such as $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i e_i p(i)$ does not change so: $dE_{\text{ave}} = 0 = \sum_i e_i dp(i)$. Here T temperature is kept constant and also the size of the box. We ask whether one may find a dot product function of probability such that $S = \sum_i p(i) G(p(i))$ changes as $dS = \sum_i G(p(i)) dp(i)$. In (2) we showed that $G(p(i)) = -\ln(p(i))$ is a solution. Thus Shannon's entropy $S = -\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ changes as a conserved average quantity when one introduces $dp(i)$. A conserved quantity, however, is stable. For the MB case, one may associate $\ln(p(i))$ with $-e_i/T$ finding $p(i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus $E_{\text{ave}} - T S = -T \ln(C(T))$. For T held constant E_{ave} and S are very similar (almost identical) and both are stable. Thus although one formally may maximize S with a constraint on E_{ave} , we argue that one really creates a function S which is essentially E_{ave} up to constant. E_{ave} is stable so S must be stable. We argue that this is the main feature of "maximized entropy".

There appears to also be another idea at work because one may add $\ln(p(i)_{\text{relative}}) = -e_i/T$ to find that $e_i + e_j$ is proportional to $\ln(p(i)p(j))$. This suggests elastic two body scattering such that $P = p(i)p(j) = \text{constant}$ if $e_i + e_j = E_{\text{constant}}$. Thus there seems to also be the idea of a loss of

information. If S is stable there must be internal restoring “forces” at work if one creates $dp(i)$. We argue that the two body scattering represents such a mechanism.

References

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